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**TIL, TA'LIM, TARJIMA
XALQARO JURNALI**

**МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ
ЯЗЫК, ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ, ПЕРЕВОД**

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OLAMNING MILLIY MANZARASINI IJODIY VA TASVIRIY AKS ETTIRISHDA MAJOZIY TIL

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada “O'tkan kunlar” romanining “Xon qiziga loyiq bir yigit” deb nomlangan bobidagi obrazli til va uning tarjima strategiyalari lingvomadaniy nuqtai nazardan tahlil qilingan. Muallifning uslubiy vositalardan foydalanishdagi badiiy mahorati hamda tarjimonning romanning asl madaniy manzarasi, maqsadlari, his-tuyg'ulari va ohanglarini saqlashga qaratilgan so'z tanlovlari qiyosiy, sifat va miqdoriy tadqiqot usullari orqali o'rganildi. Romandagi obrazli tilni sifat jihatidan baholashda M.H. Abramsning stilistik vositalar tasnifi, Q. Liu va X. Chjangning obrazli til tarjimasida qo'llaniladigan tarjima strategiyalari ta'rifidan foydalanildi. Miqdoriy baholashda esa asl matndagi har bir obrazli til elementiga ega bo'lgan gaplar soni va tarjima matndagi uchta tarjima strategiyasining qo'llanilish foizi matematik hisob-kitob yordamida aniqlandi. Ushbu tadqiqot natijalari tarjimonlik fakulteti talabalarida madaniyatga xos so'zlar, frazeologizmlar va ma'no ko'chish usullarini ingliz tiliga tarjima qilishning nazariy bilimlar va amaliy ko'nikmalarni shakllantirish uchun foydalanilishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: *lingvomadaniyat, “O'tkan kunlar”, lingvomadaniy birliklar, frazeologik birliklar, obrazli til, antonomaziya, laqab, maqollar, tarjima jarayoni, tarjima strategiyasi*

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ОБРАЗНЫЙ ЯЗЫК КАК ТВОРЧЕСКОЕ И ОБРАЗНОЕ ОТОБРАЖЕНИЕ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ КАРТИНЫ МИРА

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье анализируется образный язык и его стратегии перевода в одной главе романа «O'tkan Kunlar» («Bygone Days») под названием «Xon qiziga loyiq bir yigit» («A Young Man Suitable For The Khan's Daughter») с лингвокультурологической точки зрения. Художественное мастерство автора в использовании стилистических приемов и выбор слов переводчиком для сохранения оригинальной культурной картины романа, намерений, эмоций и тонов были изучены с помощью сравнительных, качественных и количественных исследовательских методологий. Для качественной оценки образного языка мы использовали категоризацию стилистических приемов М. Х. Абрамса, а для определения стратегий перевода, применяемых при переводе образного языка, изучали работу Цюй Лю и Сянь Чжана. Что касается количественной оценки, мы определили количество предложений с каждым стилистическим приёмом в исходном тексте и процент использования трех стратегий перевода в целевом тексте с помощью математических расчетов. Результаты данного исследования могут быть использованы для развития теоретических знаний и практических навыков студентов факультета перевода по переводу культурно-специфических слов, фразеологизмов и способов семантического переноса на английский язык.

Ключевые слова: лингвокультурология, «O'tkan Kunlar», лингвокультурологические единицы, фразеологические единицы, образный язык, антономазия, прозвище, пословицы, процесс перевода, стратегия перевода.

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FIGURATIVE LANGUAGE AS CREATIVE AND IMAGINATIVE REPRESENTATION OF NATIONAL PICTURE OF THE WORLD

ABSTRACT

This paper analyses the figurative language and its translation strategies in one chapter of the novel “O‘tkan Kunlar” (“Bygone Days”) under the title “Xon qiziga loyiq bir yigit” (A Young Man Suitable For The Khan’s Daughter) from linguocultural point of view. The author’s artistic skill of using stylistic devices and the translator’s word choices to preserve the novel’s original cultural picture, intentions, emotions and tones were examined with the help of comparative, qualitative and quantitative research methodologies. For qualitative assessment of figurative language in the novel, we used M.H.Abrams’ categorization of stylistic devices, and Q. Liu and X. Zhang’s definition of translation strategies applied in the translation of figurative language. as for the quantitative evaluation, we identified the number of sentences with each figurative language in the original text, and the percentage of the usage of three translation strategies in the target text with the help of mathematic calculations. The results of this study can be applied to develop theoretical knowledge and practical skills among translation faculty students in translating culturally specific words, phraseological units, and methods of semantic transfer into English.

Key words: *linguoculturology, “O‘tkan Kunlar”, linguoculturological units, phraseological units, figurative language, antonomasia, nickname, proverbs, translation process, translation strategy*

The Uzbek people is famous around the world for its rich, unique and vibrant culture that is revealed in our masterpieces of art and literature, lifestyle and worldview. In today’s globalized era, where the boundaries between languages and cultures are disappearing from time to time, it is vitally important to introduce our national identity to the world in its original form, i.e. without any misinterpretations. One of primary examples of such efforts is translating our classic literature masterpieces, including the works of the Uzbek romance school’s founder, Abdulla Qodiri into foreign languages. However, due to the

lexical gaps and different cultures between Uzbek and English languages, this task undoubtedly poses some challenges. More precisely, conveying adequately phraseologisms, the beauty of figurative language, national tone and cultural scenes to the English-speaking audience has several linguistic and cultural difficulties. Therefore, analyzing the translation of Uzbek literary works into the English language from linguocultural point of view and evaluating the adequacy of translator's translation choices are the tasks of our translation professionals as the representatives of the culture.

Linguoculturology is an independent branch of linguistics that was founded during the 1990's. The term "linguoculturology" appeared thanks to the scientific activities of several scholars namely Y.S.Stepanova, A.D.Arutyunova, V.V.Vorobyov and others. They were the representatives of Moscow Phraseological School under the leadership of V.N.Telia [3, 292]. According to V.A.Maslova, this new scientific discipline appeared on the basis of the idea that the language is connected to the culture. In other words, the language grows into the culture, develops within the culture and describes the culture [18, 4-5]. Linguoculturology is also connected to other disciplines such as ethnolinguistics and sociolinguistics. Even though these disciplines are closely connected to each other, they are totally different sciences.

The basic concept of linguoculturology is "culture" taking its roots from Latin word "colere" that means *cultivation, upbringing, development, veneration, cult*. Beginning from the 18th century, under the term "culture" was understood *all that appeared due to human activity and his purposeful thinking*. However, initially it meant "any kind of human impact on the nature, adjustment of nature on the interests of people". This original meaning of the word was connected to the agricultural crop. The word "culture" began to be used as a scientific term since the second half of the 18th century due to the father of anthropology, Edward Burnett Taylor's introducing it as a "complex whole which includes knowledge, belief, art, morals, law, custom, and any other capabilities and habits acquired by man as a member of society" [5, 293]. Culture cannot exist beyond human activity and social groups, in other words, it was human activity that gave a birth to such a "supernatural" means of habitat – culture. In its own turn, it was culture that created human's intellect.

From this cyclic relationship, linguoculturology recognizes the language as its research object that is considered as a basis, main condition and product of culture during human activity. An outstanding scholar, H.G.Heidegger highlighted that "not the nature or environment that is "the home to existence", but the language is; it is the language that not only reveals, but also creates the reality where humankind lives" [20, 272]. Language with its own nature leads to the analysis of the world, and its evaluation. According to G.O.Vinokur, any linguist studying the language of any given culture, becomes the very researcher of this culture.

The subject of linguoculturology is the linguistic units that have acquired symbolic, standard, figurative-metaphorical meanings in the culture recorded in

myths, legends, rituals, ceremonies, folklore and religious discourses, poetic and prose literary texts, phraseological units, proverbs and sayings.

From all abovementioned arguments, we can define that linguoculturology as a scientific discipline that appeared at the joint of linguistics and culturology, and studies the manifestation of the nation's culture that is revealed in its language. For this reason, it is not a temporary union between linguistics and culturology, but an interdisciplinary branch of science, independent with its own goals, tasks, methods, research objective and concepts [18, 17].

As we noted that linguoculturology studies the nation's culture revealed in its language, including in a figurative language, realia and lacunae, description of national cultural scenes.

Figurative language is a creative and imaginative use of words that goes beyond their literal meanings. Writers use figurative language in their works in order to create more impact on their readers, because such stylistic devices emphasize the intended message and deliver the information more effectively. Swarniti defines figurative language as “an approach to explicit a feeling or an idea by comparing two different objects, similes a thing to something has similarity in between or treat inanimate object like animate creature” [14, 14]. Ketaren and et al show four reasons why figurative language is seen more compelling to convey the message:

1) figurative language allows readers imaginative enjoyments of literary works;

2) it is a form to deliver other imagery into verse, creating the abstract concrete;

3) figurative language is able to add emotional intensity rather than merely informative statements;

4) as a tool for concentration and at the same time as a tool to state something clearly [6, 302].

G.Tajalli writes that figurative language is used to convey three aspects of the language as clarity, forthrightness and beauty [15, 100].

A lot of scholars categorized the types of figurative language differently. However, the one categorization proposed by Abrams is clearer than others, and it includes 17 types of figurative language [1, 8].

The concept “**metaphor**” has been the focus attention of researchers for ages. The first scholar to identify the existence of metaphors in human's language was Aristotitle considering it as the transfer of unordinary name either from genus to a type, or from a type to gens, or from a type to a type, or by analogy. V.N.Telia considers metaphor as “a powerful means of cognition, when we learn new things by comparing them to things we already know” [19, 129]. A.H. Yaseen includes **proverbs** and **idiomatic expressions** into the subcategories of metaphor [16, 9]. Whereas N.L.Shumsky claims that **nicknames** should also be considered metaphorically, not literally [13, 127]

Simile is an explicit comparison of two objects or events with the words like “as”, “like”, “seems”. For example, in “O'tkan kunlar”, a former mayor of Tashkent, Salimsoqbek is characterized with simile as “*qo'y kabi yuvvosh*”.

Antithesis is defined by Abrams as a contrast or opposition in the meanings of adjacent phrases or clauses that form parallelism [1, 11]. It is a strong device mostly used in proverbs and idioms. Mostly, Uzbek proverbs use antithesis to convey moral lessons, often contrasting virtue vs. vice, good vs. evil, success vs. failure. These contrasting ideas serve to guide behavior and social expectations. For example, *yaxshi bilan yomoni ajratib bo'maydi; oying o'n beshi yorug', o'n beshi qorong'u; yaxshiga kun yo'q, yomonga o'lim; o'zingni asrasang, qismatingni buzmasang*. In all of these sayings and proverbs, antonymic pairs of words are used.

Metonymy is a figurative device where the meaning of one word is closely related to another. For example, in the Uzbek phrase “*yuragini zabt etmoq*” (“to win someone’s heart”) the word “*yurak*” is used in its metonymic meaning that carries a semantics like “to reach someone’s love or reliance”.

Alliteration is the repetition of speech sounds in a sentence. It is obvious in Uzbek proverb: *suymaganga suykanma, suyganingdan ayrilma*. These words begin with the same letter that creates alliteration.

Allegory, according to Indarti and et. al., is “a story or a set of descriptive words or phrases that has a deeper meaning than its subsequent meaning” [2, 787]. In her paper, M.A.Rajapova writes that allegory is used in the Uzbek fairytale “*Ur to'qmoq*” (“Hit stick”), where the scenes of the stick hitting the bad-mannered man, the boiling jug (*qaynar xumcha*) that gives a lot of gold coins, and a magic table (*ochil dasturxon*) containing never-ending delicious food are the examples of allegory as they carry hidden moral and education for the little children [9, 154].

Allusion is when the author passes a reference to the well-known historical events, person or place. In this case, the referred person or place has the same characteristics with someone or some events. A famous Uzbek singer, Ozoda Nursaidova’s song is full of allusions: “*Beshigingda To'maris, har uyda Boburing bor*” [22]. I.V. Panasyuk also calls it as **antonomasia** [8, 55].

The need for **symbolization** is one of those needs that distinguish humankind from the wild world. We do not live in just a physical environment, but in a universe full of symbols. The world where we are living is passed to us with abundance of rituals of our first ancestors, which acted as symbols and knowledge determining their level of “culture”. Even though we do not follow many of these rituals, we have inherited the capability to symbolize from early generations. Symbols do not exist by themselves; they are the product of human consciousness. We as a microcosm create an image, a picture, a symbol of the macrocosm – the world. The relationship and connection between people is revealed in the word “symbol” itself. Initially, this Greek word denoted a *potsherd that served as a sign of friendly relations*. When parting with a guest, the host handed him half of a broken potsherd, and kept the other half for

himself. No matter how long it took for this guest to appear in the house again, he was recognized by the potsherd. “Identity card” is the original meaning of the word “symbol” in antiquity [18, 62].

Onomatopoeia is a figure of speech where a word or a group of words whose pronunciation imitates the sound of its denotation [21]. In other words, the word sounds like the action or thing it describes. For example, Uzbek onomatopoeia like *taq-tuq*, *gurs*, *jiring-jiring*, *qars-qurs*, *piq-piq*, *chak-chak* help to create vivid images or sounds in the reader’s mind.

Hyperbole is an exaggerated statement or claim that is not meant to be taken literally. It is widely used in Uzbek folk art called “lof aytish” (joke-telling). For example, “*Ikki yosh o‘g‘limning bo‘yi shunchalik o‘sib ketdiki, yulduzlarni ushlab ko‘rayapti*” (“*My two-year old son is so tall that he is touching stars*”).

Synecdoche is a figure of speech in which a part of something represents the whole, or the whole represents a part. In the Uzbek language such phrases “*dunyodan ko‘z yumdi*” or “*yuragi urishdan to‘xtadi*” (“*passed away*”) holds synecdoche.

Irony is a contrast between what is expected and what actually happens, or between what is said and what is meant. It holds secret laughter or sarcasm. In our literature, especially in poems, it has been used for a long time. For example, in the ballad “Jangchi Tursun” Hamid Olimjon used the following antiphrase (a subtype of irony): “*Erkalanib yotadi, u Vatan tuprog‘ida. Yosh bola yotganiday, onaning quchog‘ida*”. Here, the poet is describing the death of Tursun with figurative language. Even though, the words “*erkalanib yotadi*”, “*yosh bola yotganiday*”, “*onaning quchog‘ida*” have positive connotations, in these lines they are denoting the scene where a body of dead soldier is laying on the ground. From this perspective, it is irony.

Imagery is a language that appeals to the senses, helping the reader to visualize scenes, hear sounds, or experience other sensations. Abrams defines this device as “the portrayal of all the objects and aspects of sensory experience stated in a poem or other literary work” [1, 121]. Let’s take this passage from “O‘tkan Kunlar” as an example:

Ko‘rimsiz, chirk bosib qorayg‘an, juda ko‘b xizmat qilib keksaygan, ochib-yopqanda anvo‘i — turlik dodi-faryod qiladirg‘an, bunda sanalg‘an sifatlarini bir yerga jamlab natija chiqarg‘anda «sharti ketib, parti qolg‘an» bir darbozaning ostonasidan uch-to‘rt qadam ichkariga kirilsa Buxoro zindonlaridan birini his etilur va qorong‘u yo‘lakning nihoyatidagi yorug‘liqqa tomon oshiqilur [7, 13]

The description of this house’s gate and entrance corridor makes the reader use all sensory feelings to imagine this scene.

Paradox is a statement that seems self-contradictory or absurd but may actually contain truth. It can be a remark or a statement. For example, the statement “*less is more*” seems contradictory, but it suggests that simplicity can be more effective than complexity.

Personification is giving human qualities or characteristics to non-human things or abstract ideas. For example,

Lekin... lekin darbozaning qarshisidag'i mash'um tol yog'ochi unga qarab kulgandek bo'lar edi: «Boringiz, eshigim yonida to'xtamangiz, orsiz... [7, 125].

Pun is a play on words, often exploiting multiple meanings of a term or similar-sounding words for humorous effect. [1, 253] In the sentence “*I used to be a baker, but I couldn't make enough dough*”, “*dough*” refers both to *money* and to the *ingredient* in baking.

Understatement is when someone makes a statement that downplays or makes something seem less important or intense than it actually is. For example, “*It's just a scratch*” when referring to a large dent or injury.

The first novel written in Uzbek language, “*O'tkan Kunlar*” (“*Bygone Days*”) is a great, impressive and heart-breaking masterpiece of our classic literature. It is rich in figurative language, linguoculteremes, proverbs and idioms that well reflect Uzbek culture and nationality.

Our research on this novel covers only one chapter of it under the title “*Xon qiziga loyiq bir yigit*” (“*A Young Man Suitable For The Khan's Daughter*”). The reason why we chose this chapter is that Abdulla Qodiri discusses all the problems of the political and social life of those times, shows people from all layers of the society, their thinking, outlook and characteristics. As national culture is always influenced by political and social circumstances, here the heroes demonstrate a part of Uzbek lifestyle. Additionally, in this chapter, influential men gather at a party at Qutidor's and had a discussion; we can easily analyze the national figurative language in their speeches.

The first stage of our research was devoted to the identification of stylistic devices and phraseologisms in their speeches. We found 75 cases of figurative language. Table 1 presents the frequency and presentation of occurrence of figurative language, listed from the most to the least.

Table 1

Figurative language in chapter “Xon qiziga loyiq bir yigit” (“A Young Man Suitable For The Khan’s Daughter”) of “O‘tkan Kunlar” (“Bygone Days”)

№	Figurative language	Frequency	Presentation (%)
1.	Idiom	32	40 %
2.	Metaphor	17	21.25 %
3.	Personification	7	8.75 %
4.	Irony	5	6.25 %
5.	Proverbs/sayings	4	5 %
6.	Symbol	3	3.75 %
7.	Simile	2	2.5 %
8.	Metonymy	2	2.5 %
9.	Paradox	2	2.5 %
10.	Nickname	2	2.5 %
11.	Hyperbole	1	1.25 %
12.	Allegory	1	1.25 %
13.	Understatement	1	1.25 %
14.	Antonomasia	1	1.25 %
	Total	80	100 %

As can be seen from Table 1, there are 80 sentences contain stylistic devices. Fourteen out of seventeen figurative languages proposed by Abrams are found. The emerging can be reviewed as follows: the majority type of figurative language in chapter “Xon qiziga loyiq bir yigit” are idiomatic expressions and simple metaphors, with 32 (or 40 %) and 17 (or 21.25 %) cases correspondingly. Simile, metonymy, paradox and nickname equally occur in 2 cases or 2.5 %, while hyperbole, allegory, understatement and antonomasia are found with the less frequency (only 1 case and 1.25 %). There are 7 examples of personification with 8.75 % of presentation, 5 cases of irony (6.25 %), 4 sentences holding proverbs (5 %) and 3 cases of symbol (3.75 %) in this chapter.

The next stage of the research involved analyzing and evaluating the translation strategies of these stylistic devices employed in the novel’s English translation, “Bygone Days” produced by American writer and translator Mark Reese. Below we will bring some examples for each figurative language with their translations.

Idioms.

1. *Otabek o‘zi bilan ko‘rishgan mundaki ikki yot kishini tanimaganliqdan bir-ikki qayta ularni ko‘z ostidan kechirdi* [7, 5].

Otabek’s eyes passed again and again over the two strangers greeting him – clearly showing wariness about their intentions... [11, 32].

In this example, the idiomatic expression “*ko‘z ostidan kechirmoq*” meaning “to look over carefully” is translated with an equivalent idiom “*eyes passed over*”. This translation method is **transference**, as the translator tries to save the existence of idiomatic expression in the sentence with the help of substitutions.

2. “*Itoatdan bosh tortmasin...*” degan mulohazada yozg‘an shikoyatlarimizdan markazning *ko‘z yumishi ham ehtimoldir* [7, 7].

All our complaints are based on the hope that Azizbek will acquiesce to Qoqan’s power, but it could be that Qoqan is turning a blind eye to our petitions for redress [11, 34-35].

Here the Uzbek idiomatic expression “*itoatdan bosh tortmasin*” is replaced with an ordinary verb phrase “to acquiesce to someone” using **rephrasing** strategy. Moreover, the translator has applied an antonymic translation shifting from negative sentence structure to a positive.

Another idiomatic expression “*shikoyatga ko‘z yummoq*” meaning “to deliberately ignore or disregard something” is well preserved with its English idiomatic substitution “to turn blind eyes”.

3. *Ziyo shohichi bilan o‘g‘li Rahmatning har zamon mehmonlarni dasturxonga qistashlari boshqalarning ishtahalarini ochishg‘a sabab bo‘lsa ham, ammo bizning Otabekka sira ham asar qilmas, xayollanib o‘ltirar edi* [7, 7].

Ziyo shohichi and Rahmat urged on the guests’ appetites by encouraging them to take more – Oling, Olinglar! – yet Otabek ate very little and sat seemingly lost in a daydream [11, 35].

In this interesting passage, the translator has used all his artistic skills to convey the initial message and preserve the national scenario of having a party in Uzbek society. Firstly, let’s analyze the translation of the idiomatic expression “*dasturxonga qistamoq*”. The idiomatic expression “**dasturxonga qistamoq**” literally means “to push someone to the table” or “to urge someone to sit at the dining table”. In this context, it refers to encouraging or urging someone to eat. The translator has translated this idiom as “to encourage the guests to take more” and has added extra information about how Uzbek people encourage the guests to take more by pronouncing the words “*Oling, Olinglar!*” literally meaning “please take, take more!” The translation method used here is **expansion** and **explanatory translation**. We should thank Mark Reese for his dedication to provide explanations for such kind of cultural words and phrases at the end of his book in the section “Endnotes”. He has given explanations to more than four hundred concepts. He has explained this “*Oling, Olinglar!*” as follows:

“Oling, Olinglar!” literally means “Take, take everyone,” bt it is a common enjoinder by the host to his guests to eat their fill – again, usually repeated three times [11, 438].

Metaphors

1. *Shamayda ekanman, qanotim bo'lsa, vatanga uchsam, to'ppa-to'g'ri xon o'rdasiga tushsam-da, o'risning hukumat qonunlarini birma-bir arz qilsam,...* [7, 8].

When I was in Shamai, I thought that if I had wings, I would fly to my motherland, I would descend directly upon the khan's palace and implement each and every one of Russian's governmental policies [11, 36].

The metaphor “if I had wings, I would fly to my motherland” works in a similar way in both English and Uzbek. It uses the idea of flying to show a strong feeling of wanting to return to a place, like the homeland as fast as possible. Thus, the translator uses **literal translation** preserving both semantics and structure of the metaphor. According to Q. Liu and X. Zhang, literary translation is a good choice when two languages share the same vehicle and tenor with the same meaning [4, 123]

2. ... *aqlsiz bir go'dakni (Xudoyorni) xon ko'tarib el yelkasiga mindi* [7, 8].

Impetuous Khudayar Khan, a mere child, became khan through Musulmaql's backing. Throughout this entire period he rode on the shoulders of population [11, 37].

In this passage, the metaphor “aqlsiz bir go'dak” is referring to the idea of someone who is naive, immature or lacking in wisdom. In the translation, this description of the khan lost its metaphorical context. It is just **simplified** into an ordinary adjective phrases *impetuous mere child* that just implies youth and inexperience, leaving out the specific reference to a lack of intelligence or sensibility. According to M. Yazici “**simplification** does not mean stylistic impoverishment, on the contrary it is a translatorial operation to disambiguate the information load of the text by operating procedures at different levels: lexical, syntactic and stylistic. Accordingly, it is a way of covert introduction of new knowledge without distracting the reader's attention” [17; 1101].

Irony

Kechiringiz, amak, — deb Otabek kulimsiradi,— siz otamning mushovirlig'ini boshqacharoq onгла-g'ang'a o'xshadingiz... [7, 6]

“Alas, Amak,” said Otabek, smiling. “You seem to have misjudged the importance of my father's rank.” [11, 35]

In the original context, the ironic tone is expressed with the words “*Kechiringiz... kulimsirab*”. This is the case for the Uzbek people to prove others' statements or comments on something are not appropriate in a polite way. Yet, they convey their message in an ironic tone. The same ironic tone is preserved in the translation with the use of English word “Alas”, however it lacks the politeness. Instead, it may express sorrow or regret. This choice of the translator is explained as transference method, as it best fits for the context in the target language.

Proverbs and sayings

1. *Umr otilgan o'q emish* [7, 6].

Life seems to have shot past like an arrow [11, 33].

2. *Yurgan daryo, o'lturgan bo'ryo emish* [7, 7]

Those who walk are a river; those who sit are reed mat [11, 35]

In the translation of proverbs, Mark Reese prefers literal translation. This approach does not use equivalent English proverbs with different vehicles and tenors but with the same meaning. However, it shows national colorit of Uzbek proverbs, that how this nation express a particular experience in their proverbs. Therefore, we consider this approach to be successful, even though the translation context does not hold proverbs.

Symbolism

1. *Bu yerda so'zimni eshitkuchi birov ham bo'lmadi, bo'lsalar ham: "Sening orzungni shu xonlar eshitadimi, shu beklar ijro qiladimi?" deb meni ma'yus qildilar. Ilgariroq men ularning gapiga bovar qilmay yursam, so'ngg'idan to'g'ri so'zni aytkanlarini bildim. Darhaqiqat, mozoristonda «hayya alalfalah» xitobini kim eshitar edi* [7, 8].

No one would listen to me. Even when there were people who were willing to listen, they would retort, "Will the khans listen to our dreams, and will the beks even carry the them out?" With this simple question they shattered my dreams. At first I could not fathom that they actually believed their own words, but later I found that they spoke the truth. Indeed, who will listen to the prayers of the dead baring their soul to the living? Will those already buried in a cemetery listen to calls for help? Who will listen?[11, 36]

In this passage, unfortunately, the translator misinterprets the metaphorical expression "hayya alalfalah" as "call for help". "Hayya alalfalah" is a part of Muslim call for prayer, literally meaning "come to salvation", but not "come to help". In Muslim ideology, prayer is a salvation from sorrows and sufferings of hereafter life and in the call for prayer there is not any call for help. Otabek is comparing his offers and suggestions for improvement of his motherland to "hayya alalfalah". He is metaphorically calling the khans to salvation, not to help. And the khans are not listening to his words as if they were dead, like those buried in the cemetery cannot hear "hayya alalfalah" and respond to it by committing the prayer on time. Therefore, "hayya alalfalah" is the symbol of Otabek's intentions for his motherland, and the cemetery symbolizes of those times' Turkistan, where the dead symbolize the khans and population of this country. From this point of view, we found this translation inaccurate, as it cannot convey the true intentions of the author.

Rashidova D.K. writes that "religious language is characterized by inertia, as it has the same and unchangeable terms and concepts. Moreover, the attempt of generating new terms or concepts is risky, because of the severe criticism from the part of religious scholars. This is why a translator of religious texts has to be careful in the process of *word selection*".[10, 632] Therefore, we would offer to remain original symbolic term "hayya alalfalah" in the text, and give a detailed explanation in section "Endnotes" about what "hayya alalfalah" literally means and why Otabek is comparing the khans to the dead, and his words to the call for *salvation*.

2. *Istiqbol qayg'usi tushiga ham kirmagan bu Turkiston otalari Otabekning daruni dildan chiqarib aytgan gaplaridan hissasiz qolmadilar* [7, 8].

These "Fathers of Turkistan", who had never even considered such a course for their motherland, fervently latched onto Otabek's vision of a future that rose deep from within pure heart and was clearly expressed with the most sublime intentions [11, 36].

In this context the phrase "**Turkiston otalari**" literally translates into "**Fathers of Turkistan**". This metaphorical term is symbolizing important leaders or respected people from the region of Turkistan. These leaders had authority over the people, politics and culture. The translator has used **calque** method of translating. Calquing involves translating a foreign expression *word-for-word* or by its components into another language. The structure or meaning is directly transferred, but the individual words are translated into the target language.

Personification

1. ... *lekin Shamay manim fikrimni ost-ust qilib, o'zimni ham butunlay boshqa kishi yasadi* [7, 7].

... but my travels there changed this opinion. My experiences deeply affected my beliefs about life, transforming me [11, 36]

In this sentence, even personification is saved, the original message has undergone **lexical and grammatical transformations** to make the sentence more appropriate for the target audience. It is obvious in the case where instead of "*Shamai*", there is used the word "*my travels there*", and the phrase "*o'zimni ham boshqa kishi yasadi*" is replaced with "*transformed me*". This is a natural way of expressing personal changes under the experiences in the English language. Moreover, in the original context the word "*fikrim*" is a general notion, whereas the translator has explained it with more **concrete** words "*my beliefs about life*". This method in translation is called **concretization**. E.V. Shapkina and D.A. Shapkin explain that concretization is "used in translating words with wide and non-differential meaning. It means translating words of source language by words with specified concrete meaning in the target language" [12, 49].

2. *Bizning idoramiz bu kungi tartibsizligi bilan ketabersa...* [7, 7]

... if our government continues with this current anarchy [11, 36]

In this translation, on the contrary, both the figurative language and the structure are preserved, by the same time staying true to the meaning of the message. Therefore, it is a literal translation method.

Simile

1. *Men o'risning idora ishlarini ko'rib, o'z idoramizning xuddi bir o'yinchoq bo'lg'anlig'ini iqror etishka majbur bo'ldim...* [7, 7]

When I saw the Russian government's policies. I realized that our leadership's approach and tenets are frivolous, as if we are playing at governance [11, 36].

The translation of simile “*idoramizning xuddi bir o‘yinchoq bo‘lg‘anlig‘i*” keeps the meaning of the simile but changes the image a little. Instead of translating it as “like a toy” directly, the translator uses the phrase “*as if we are playing at governance*”. This chosen variant shows the idea of something being unimportant or pretended not seriously, but it replaces the image of a toy (something physical) with the more general action of “*playing*”. It is because that the translator tries to meet the target readers’ expectations using more natural language.

Metonymy

Otabek majliska tamoman yangi va eshitilmagan fikrlarni so‘zlab ketdi, ... [7, 8]
Otabek continued to expound on innovative and unprecedented ideas to the men at the gathering, ... [11, 37].

The word "majlis" in the original sentence refers to the gathering itself, but here it is used to mean the people at the gathering. This is an example of **metonymy**, where the place or event (the gathering) stands for the people who are part of it. The translator changes “majlis” to “the men at the gathering” to make it clearer who Otabek is speaking to. This method is **explicit rephrasing** that results in the loss of the metonymical expression of the original context.

Paradox

Otabek xon qizig‘a loyiq yigit ekan [7, 9].

Otabek is suitable for a khan’s daughter [11, 39].

In this passage, the characterization of Otabek by other guests at the gathering contains paradox, or a contrasting idea to understand. To put it in other words, due to his gentle features and intellect, critical thinking abilities, he is considered to be worthy of a khan’s daughter, despite his lower status than a princess. The literal translation of the sentence preserves both structure and meaning of the original message.

Hyperbole

Agarda xon ko‘tarish manim qo‘limda bo‘lsa edi, xon qilib Otabekni ko‘tarar edim... [7, 9].

If it were in my power to appoint rulers, I would make him a khan ... [11, 38].

Here, this statement looks like a paradox. However, the construction of conditional sentence allows understanding that it is a dream, not a factual statement. Therefore, it is a hyperbole about Otabek’s intellect, education and dedication to motherland. The translation is obviously literal that is conveying the same structure and semantics, and saves the figurativeness of the sentence as well.

Allegory

Otasining bolasi-da [7, 9].

He is indeed his father’s son [11, 38].

While giving characteristics to Otabek, Ziyo Shohichi is referring directly to his father. It means that he is allegorically evaluating Otabek’s father, but not

himself. This is also an example of literal translation where the structure and the meaning is preserved.

Understatement

... *bundog' yigitlar uylanganlarida ham kishi qizini umr bo'yi azob ichida o'tkazadirlar...* [7, 9].

People of his sort make girls suffer even if they do finally marry... [11, 38].

Hamid's characteristics of Otabek is underestimating his personal features, and therefore it is understatement. The translation saves the figurativeness, yet softens the original level of ironic tone by omitting the part "*umr bo'yi*".

Antonomasia

Amiri Umarxondek odil poshsho bo'lsa, biz ham o'risdan oshib tushar edik [7, 8].

If we had a khan like Umar Khan, we would overtake those Russians [11, 36].

Here, a speaker is directly referring to a historical figure famous in the area. Even though the translation renders the same message by preserving antonomasia in the sentence with the help of **literal translation**, it has omitted the well-known feature of that person "*odil*". According to the rule of allusion or antonomasia, the referred person or object's features or characteristics should be mentioned in the sentence. However, the translation does not hold this information about Umar Khan. Therefore, it may somehow lose the figurativeness, because the target audience who is unfamiliar with Uzbek history and personality of Umar Khan may not understand why he is referred in this context.

Nickname

Musulmon cho'loq [7, 6].

Muslim Cho'loq [11, 33].

Here, a nickname acquired for the physical disability is used in this context. The translation, instead of finding a substitution in the English language, prefers to borrow this term and uses the method of **loanwords**.

We may classify all the strategies used to translate the figurative language into three categories: literal translation, transference and meaning translation. Literal translation may be used, when there are the same vehicles and tenors are used to express a particular meaning; transference is an appropriate strategy when there is a substitution of original figurative language in the target language (this alternative has the same meaning, even though it conveys different expression); and meaning translation is applicable when there is no chance to translate literally or any alternative substitution in the target language, it includes all the strategies that help to render the intention and meaning of the original text with any kind of tools.

The third stage of our research was devoted to identify the percentage of each category of translation strategies used in rendering the 80 figurative languages found in chapter "Xon qiziga loyiq bir yigit" ("A Young Man

Suitable For The Khan's Daughter”) of “O'tkan Kunlar” (“Bygone Days”). Figure 1 demonstrates the percentage of usage of strategy.

Figure 1

As one can see from the diagram, the most used category of strategy of translating figurative language in chapter “Xon qiziga loyiq bir yigit” (“A Young Man Suitable For The Khan’s Daughter”) of “O’tkan Kunlar” (“Bygone Days”) is meaning translation with 44% of usage (35 cases). It is explained by the fact that most Uzbek words and phrases, including stylistic devices cannot be always translated into English with literal or substitutional equivalences. In order to convey the message of the original figurative language, the translator needs address other methods as calque, rephrasing, simplification, generalization, loanwords and even omission which we included into the one category, meaning translation. Literal translation is also used in a lot of cases (36.25% with 29 cases) in order to introduce the target audience the style of beautifying the language of the Uzbek nation. The less used strategy was transference with only 20%, or more exactly being used in 16 cases, that can be explained by the effort of the translator not to destroy the Uzbek picture of the novel by employing too much English phrases.

Conclusion

Summing all the results acquired in our research, it can be said that in chapter “Xon qiziga loyiq bir yigit” (“A Young Man Suitable For The Khan’s Daughter”) in the novel “O’tkan Kunlar” (“Bygone Days”) idioms and metaphors are the majority types of figurative language. Additionally, meaning translation and literal translation strategies are mostly used to translate the figurative language in literary works as they preserve both meaning and structure, and the national picture of the original work. It lets target readers to

become acquainted with the culture and linguistic features of a foreign nation by the means of literature. Transference strategy, although a creative method, may result in the loss of national colorit of the source novel.

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